

Migration, Integration, Citizenship in Belgium between 1990 and 2018: The State of the Art

Country Report: Belgium

By

Dr. Ayşe Tecmen

ERC AdG PRIME Youth Post-doc Researcher

İstanbul Bilgi University

European Institute

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Introduction

This literature review provides a discussion of the significant developments in Belgium's immigration and integration policies between 1990 and 2018.¹ The paper is written within the framework of the ERC Advanced Grant Project titled "Nativism, Islamophobia and Islamism in the Age of Populism: Culturalisation and Religionisation of what is Social, Economic and Political in Europe"² (ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM).³

This paper focuses on the Muslim-origin migrants as there is a long history of emigration from Turkey and Morocco to Belgium⁴. This review follows significant developments such as elections, new discourses, the rise of populism and the rising terrorist threats in the country in a chronological manner. However, it does not assess the impact and reception of these elements from the perspective of the migrant communities. It rather constitutes a study into the context which has shaped the experiences of migrants and their descendants.

In doing so, this review delineates the five legal channels of movement to Belgium; namely free movement of EU citizens; family reunions; foreign students; foreign workers; as well as refugees and asylum seekers. In line with these diverse channels, we follow the changes in migration and integration policies in Flanders and Wallonia, focusing on the case of Flanders to review the literature on Muslim-origin youth.

¹ I would like to thank Ayhan Kaya, An Van Raemdonck, and Ayşenur Benevento for their support, suggestions and remarks during the writing of this report.

² This project with the acronym of "ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM" has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme grant agreement no. 785934. This research analyses the current political, social, and economic context of the European Union, which is confronted by two substantial crises, namely the global financial crisis and the refugee crisis. These crises have led to the escalation of fear and prejudice among the youth who are specifically vulnerable to discourses that culturalise and stigmatize the "other". Young people between the ages of 18 to 30, whether native or immigrant-origin, have similar responses to globalization-rooted threats such as deindustrialization, isolation, denial, humiliation, precariousness, insecurity, and anomia. These responses tend to be essentialised in the face of current socio-economic, political and psychological disadvantages. While a number of indigenous young groups are shifting to right-wing populism, a number of Muslim youths are shifting towards Islamic radicalism. The common denominator of these groups is that they are both downwardly mobile and inclined towards radicalization. Hence, this project aims to scrutinize social, economic, political and psychological sources of the processes of radicalization among native European youth and Muslim-origin youth with migration background, who are both inclined to express their discontent through ethnicity, culture, religion, heritage, homogeneity, authenticity, past, gender and patriarchy.

³ All State of the Art reports are available at: <https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/en/publications/archive/>

⁴ In the scope of the "ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM" project, Lalla Amina Drhimeur (2020a, 2020b) has provided an extensive literature review on the Moroccan-origin migrants in France, Germany, Belgium and the Netherlands. See <https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/en/publications/state-art-moroccan-emigration-europe/>

Background

In 1830 Belgium gained its independence from the Netherlands; it was occupied by Germany during World Wars I and II. It has been influenced by both the German and Latin world, which explains the linguistic and cultural plurality that is observed in the country. Owing to the reforms between 1970 and 2001, the country evolved into a federal structure which occurred through five state reforms (in 1970, 1980, 1988-89, 1993 and 2001). The federal structure is also guaranteed under the first Article of the Belgian constitution, which reads: 'Belgium is a federal state, composed of communities and regions'.

The laws enacted between 1873 and 1963 recognise French, Dutch and German as official languages of Belgium. Thus, the current federal structure is composed of three linguistic/cultural communities (French, Dutch and German, respectively). With the Revision of the Constitution on May 5 1993, the Federal State was created, and three regions (Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital) were recognised. This structure, which established the federal, regional, and linguistic community as different levels of government, also means that the federal government and the federal parliament do not have the exclusive right to make decisions and there are various partners, who independently exercise their authority within their given domains, which creates a complex division of responsibilities. The federal-state competencies include foreign affairs, defence, justice, finance, social security, as well as an important part of public health and domestic affairs.⁵ Because of historical, cultural, economic and political differences between populations, the regions formed very different ways of belonging to Belgium. Notwithstanding cultural disparities, Belgium retained its political unity and became a new model emphasising the political rather than the cultural or the national (Kaya and Kentel 2009: 16).

Figure 1: Linguistic Communities in Belgium

Source: Gysen, Kuijper, and Van Avermaet, 2009: 102.

⁵ Further information on the federalisation of Belgium is available at: https://www.belgium.be/en/about_belgium/government/federale_staat

According to 2011 estimates, ethnic groups in Belgium are Belgian 75%, Italian 4.1%, Moroccan 3.7%, French 2.4%, Turkish 2%, Dutch 2%, other 12.8%.⁶ Subsequently, in 2011 the percentages of the total population speaking each language as a *first language* are Dutch (official) 60%, French (official) 40%, German (official) less than 1% (ibid). And according to the 2009 estimates, religious affiliation percentages are as follows: Roman Catholic 50%, Protestant and other Christian 2.5%, Muslim 5%, Jewish 0.4%, Buddhist 0.3%, atheist 9.2%, none 32.6% (ibid). Furthermore, the number of Muslims in Belgium have remained relatively similar, which was 6,3% in 2011, rising to 7,2% in 2016 (see Table 1). In 2016, the number of Turks and Moroccans in Belgium were 268.509 and 494.940 respectively, with a total of 763.449.

Table 1. % Muslims in Belgium, regions and provinces 2011-2016

	1/01/2011	1/01/2013	1/01/2015	1/01/2016
	% moslims	% moslims	% moslims	% moslims
België	6,3%	6,5%	7,0%	7,2%
Vlaams Gewest	4,5%	4,7%	5,1%	5,4%
Brussels Gewest	22,4%	22,6%	23,6%	24,2%
Waals Gewest	4,4%	4,5%	4,9%	5,1%
Antwerpen	6,6%	6,9%	7,5%	7,8%
Vlaams-Brabant	3,1%	3,3%	3,7%	3,9%
West-Vlaanderen	1,6%	1,8%	2,1%	2,3%
Oost-Vlaanderen	4,4%	4,5%	5,0%	5,2%
Limburg	6,0%	5,9%	6,3%	6,6%
Brussels Gewest	22,4%	22,6%	23,6%	24,2%
Waals-Brabant	2,3%	2,3%	2,6%	2,7%
Henegouwen	5,0%	5,2%	5,7%	5,8%
Luik	6,2%	6,3%	6,8%	7,2%
Luxemburg	1,5%	1,5%	1,8%	1,9%
Namen	1,7%	1,7%	1,9%	2,0%

Source: <http://www.npdata.be/BuG/355-Verkiezingen-1/Verkiezingen-1.htm>

⁶ Source: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/geos/be.html>

Table 2. Turks and Moroccans in Belgium, the regions and the provinces in 2016

Naam	Aantallen			% op bevolking		
	Turkse	Marokk.	Totaal	% Turks	% Marokk.	Totaal
België	268.509	494.940	763.449	2,4%	4,4%	6,8%
Vlaams Gewest	145.504	178.759	324.263	2,2%	2,8%	5,0%
Brussels Gewest	59.881	223.168	283.049	5,0%	18,8%	23,8%
Waals Gewest	63.125	92.955	156.079	1,8%	2,6%	4,3%
Antwerpen	34.802	98.357	133.159	1,9%	5,4%	7,3%
Vlaams-Brabant	12.171	25.908	38.079	1,1%	2,3%	3,4%
West-Vlaanderen	2.181	12.163	14.344	0,2%	1,0%	1,2%
Oost-Vlaanderen	47.514	25.256	72.770	3,2%	1,7%	4,9%
Limburg	48.836	17.075	65.911	5,7%	2,0%	7,6%
Brussels Gewest	59.881	223.168	283.049	5,0%	18,8%	23,8%
Waals-Brabant	853	7.749	8.602	0,2%	2,0%	2,2%
Henegouwen	33.638	36.285	69.923	2,5%	2,7%	5,2%
Luik	26.046	42.005	68.051	2,4%	3,9%	6,3%
Luxemburg	921	2.344	3.265	0,3%	0,8%	1,2%
Namen	1.666	4.571	6.237	0,3%	0,9%	1,3%

Source: <http://www.npdata.be/BuG/355-Verkiezingen-1/Verkiezingen-1.htm>

Non-EU immigration to Belgium began first with Southern European migrants (such as from Spain, Italy and Greece) and later with Moroccans and Turks who were recruited in the 1960s to work in the coal mines. The Belgian government signed up several bilateral agreements to bring in foreign labour to compensate for the declining domestic workforce. The first agreement was signed with Italy in 1946, the with Spain in 1956, Greece in 1957, Morocco and Turkey in 1964, Tunisia in 1969, Algeria in 1970, and Yugoslavia in 1970 (Wets, 2006; Kaya and Kentel, 2009). After the Royal Decree of 1936, immigration to Belgium was facilitated between 1963 and 1967 through cooperation between the Ministry of Justice and Foreigners Police. Employers were entitled to hire immigrants through a work permit issued in their country of origin or a work permit obtained in Belgium after entering the country with a tourist visa (Kaya, 2009, 2012). This strategy had different objectives such as filling the demographic deficit and drawing immigrants to Belgium rather than rival countries like Germany, France and the Netherlands. This family grouping strategy also helped to keep immigrants' incomes within the Belgian economy, instead of being sent to their countries of origin (De Raedt, 2004: 15).

In many European countries, such as in Germany, the Turkish community is one of the largest minority groups (Kaya, 2012). Nonetheless, despite their long-term presence, they remain marginalised in the host societies, and they are perceived as failing to integrate or failing to find a position within the host society (Wets, 2006). Turkish migrants in Belgium mainly originate from a cluster of central Anatolian provinces, and nearly 60 percent of first-generation Turkish migrants living in Belgium was born in the countryside or a small village (Wets 2006: 94). Most Turkish immigrants originate from Afyon, Eskisehir and Kayseri and one-third of Belgium's Turkish-origin immigrants are from Emirdağ in Afyon (ibid). The Turkish community in Belgium is composed of persons of diverse ethnic, religious and

cultural backgrounds, including Turks of Kurdish origin, Christians, Sunnis, and Alevis (Wets, 2006: 93-94, see also Kaya and Kentel, 2009).

Contrary to some other immigrant groups, Turks settled just about everywhere and are distributed equally over the urban areas of the country, in Brussels and Antwerp, but especially in Ghent and Limburg. Furthermore, as the Walloon industrial basins drastically declined in the 1970s, immigrant flows originated from Italy, Spain, Turkey and Maghreb were reoriented to large cities (especially Brussels) (Debuisson, Docquier, Noury and Nantcho 2004: 7).

Immigration flows to Belgium have been strongly linked to the economic context, and they are considered in the context of labour migration as migrants fulfil the need for workers in certain sectors. Due to the oil crisis in 1974, the foreign population structure changed, and the number of newcomers declined between 1974 and 1980. As will be shown below as well, “family reunion” became an important motive in terms of migration channels. Since the late 1980s, the number of asylum seekers and refugees also increased significantly (Debuisson, Docquier, Noury and Nantcho 2004: 6).

The reorientation of Turkish migrants to major cities was a result of the economic recession and the oil crisis, which struck the coal industry leading to increased unemployment. After the mines were closed, it was difficult for the Turkish miners to adapt to the labour market because they did not speak Flemish or French (Wets, 2006: 94).

Responsibility for immigrant integration and labour market issues was transferred to the regions and linguistic communities after the end of immigration in 1974. Belgium was the forerunner in Europe in starting a public debate to secure immigrants’ residency status and grant them political rights in 1969, such as the right to vote and to stand for local elections. Consultative Immigrant Communal Councils (*Conseils Communaux Consultatifs des Immigrés*, CCCI, *Stedelijke Migrantenraden*) were formed in several cities to serve as liaison committees between immigrants and city authorities (Martiniello, 1997: 108-110).

Moroccans and Turks stayed in the country and, although there was a moratorium for labour migration, new immigrants from Morocco and Turkey kept on entering the country through the process of family reunification and family formation. The Belgian government in the mid-1980s acknowledged the fact that the expected temporary migration seemed to have a more permanent character and started designing policies to enable immigrants to settle in the country and integrate into society. The law on foreigners entering, living, settling and returning, which is still in effect, was passed in December 1980. This law offered greater legal clarity as regards residency and established a legal mechanism for foreigners to challenge measures that suspected the legality of their stay (Wets 2006: 94).

The between 1974 and 1989 also marked the first stage of the institutionalisation of Islam, which was distinct from its counterparts in Germany and France. As Kaya and Kentel (2009: 17) argue through direct official interventions, Belgian, Turkish, Moroccan and Saudi states were active in establishing an Islamic presence in the region and many Belgian-Muslims were disturbed by such undisguised influence from outside. The Belgian state subsequently changed its policy towards Muslims in the 1990s, as the Belgian-Muslims faced major

“structural problems including discrimination, high unemployment, crime, exclusion and social deprivation” (ibid).

In 1984, then Minister of Justice, Jean Gol, initiated new legislation to shape the pillars of Belgian immigration law. The Gol Legislation of June 28, 1984, had three aspirations: a) restricting illegal immigration; b) repatriating some immigrants; and c) integrating some immigrants by naturalisation. The new legislation introduced equality to migrant men and women before the law, allowed mothers to freely transfer their Belgian nationality to their children and strengthened the concept of Belgian nationality merit (Kaya and Kentel, 2009: 17). The new Nationality Code introduced the principle of *jus soli* (law of the soil) and simplified the procedure for naturalisation. Children born on Belgian soil to foreign parents who themselves were born in Belgium became Belgian citizens. Although simplified, the naturalisation process still required individuals to demonstrate a “desire to integrate” measured arbitrarily by the administration. The right to political participation of the migrant communities was heavily debated. The government decided not to grant political rights, but to relax the conditions for acquiring Belgian nationality. The electoral success of the *Vlaams Blok* in the city of Antwerp in the 1989 elections (for more information on the *Vlaams Blok* see Swyngedouw and Ivaldi, 2001; Walgrave and De Swert, 2004; Billiet and De Witte, 1995; Swyngedouw, 1998; Kaya, 2019) led to the creation of a government service that would monitor the position of the immigrant population called the Royal Commissioner for the Policy on Immigrants (see also Mandin, 2014). This task has been taken up since 1990 by the successor organisation, the Center for Equal Opportunities and the Fight against Racism.

Between 1989 and 1995 marks the second period of the institutionalisation of Islam during which Islam was part of a mixed approach combining Walloon class-oriented integration policies and Flemish multiculturalist policies focusing on ethnicity (Ireland, 2000: 252). After the Royal Commission on Migrant Policy terminated the authorisation of the Islamic and Cultural Center (ICC) that was established by Muslims in 1968, it established the

the Council of Experts, approved a Technical Committee in 1990, charged with appointing or reappointing Islamic instruction teachers, to begin in the 1990-91 school year. This decision put an end to the authority of the ICC to appoint teachers, a decision which amounted to government interference in Islam’s organisational structure, because only the governing body of a religion is legally allowed to appoint teachers (Kaya and Kentel, 2009: 17).

The Nationality Code was revised again and passed in its new form on March 1, 2000. Since then, any foreigner legally residing for at least seven years in Belgium who has a permanent residence permit can become Belgian with a simple declaration without a check on his or her “desire to integrate.” (Wets 2006: 94). Between 1995 and 2000, marked the third phase of the institutionalisation of Islam during which a more technical and judicial approach was employed.

During this period, Muslims were asked to organise elections for the *Exécutif des Musulmans de Belgique*. In the first elections, held in 1998, Moroccans were overrepresented in the Muslim Council. However, in the 2004 elections, Turks were broadly mobilised to become candidates and to vote. The result was that 40 of the

68 members of the Council elected were Belgian-Turks and 20 Moroccans. Moroccan participation in the elections dramatically declined due to the fact that elected members of the Council were subject to confirmation by the Belgian government (Kaya and Kentel, 2009: 17).⁷

Moreover, in 2015 a new (modified) Code, entered into force on January 1 2013, containing stricter and more difficult rules. Subsequently, in 2015, 26,238 foreigners acquired Belgian nationality. In recent years, the number of acquisitions of the Belgian nationality fluctuated between 18,000 and 38,000 a year.

Five legal channels of migration to Belgium

As noted above, as in many European countries, 1974 marks a decisive turn in migration policies in Belgium, which still influence current migration patterns. In 1974, the Council of Ministers made three critical decisions: i) it officially stopped any new immigration of workers; ii) it took measures to control clandestine immigration; iii) it regularised a few thousand undocumented migrant workers (Martiniello, 2003: 225). As Marco Martiniello writes (2003), despite the fact that there has not been a political acknowledgement of Belgium as a country of immigration, migration to Belgium mainly continues under the following five *legal* channels:⁸

- a) **free movement of EU citizens:** EU law allows for citizens' mobility within the member states "In public discourse, the issue of the free movement of EU citizens and the issues of immigration are increasingly separated, the latter being reserved for non-EU migrants. In any case, the number of French and Dutch citizens who have decided to work and live in Belgium has constantly increased over the last ten years" (ibid: 226),
- b) **family reunions:** "Foreigners who are legally settled in Belgium have the right to bring in spouses and children (under 18 years old) and in certain specific conditions, other family members. Family reunion is important since many immigrant-origin youths marry a partner from the country of origin during the summer holidays. It also concerns Belgian citizens or EU citizens who want to bring in their non-EU spouses or children" (ibid: 226-227),
- c) **foreign students:** "Belgium grants yearly temporary residence permits to foreign students. In theory, their residence permits expire at the end of their studies" (ibid: 227).
- d) **foreign workers:** "foreign workers receive each year the right to come and work in Belgium. There are two types of work permits for foreign workers: the work permit A and the work permit B. The work permit A is unlimited in time and is valid for all salaried jobs and professions. The applicant must prove either five years of legal residence in Belgium without interruption in the period before the application or four years of work without interruption and covered by a work permit B in the same

⁷ For further information on *Exécutif des Musulmans de Belgique* see <https://www.embnet.be/>.

⁸ Furthermore, Belgium is also a country of passage for migrants who want to reach the United Kingdom and, from there, North America (Martiniello 2003: 228).

period. The work permit B is limited to one year and is renewable under specific conditions. With a work permit B, the foreign worker is only granted the authorisation to work for one employer in cases of nonavailability of a Belgian or EU worker to fulfil a position” (ibid: 227).

- e) **refugees and asylum seekers** (for a similar overview of the five main ways of entering into Belgium see Debuissin, Docquier, Noury & Nantcho, 2004: 9).

As in many other European countries, refugees and asylum seekers remain one of the most significant topics in terms of reception and integration in Belgium. Asylum procedures in Belgium have been modified several times between 1987 and 2000, which was influenced by the broader European asylum and refugee debate. For instance, “the 1987 Belgian initiative concerning the imposition of sanctions on transporters who bring asylum candidates without papers into the Belgian territory, for example, preceded by a few weeks a decision by the European ministers charged with immigration affairs” (Martiniello 2003: 228). Belgium has since followed other European states’ direction, as was the case in the provisions of 1991, 1993 and 1996 (ibid). To that end, most recently at the legislative level, the Reception Conditions Directive which was adopted in 2013 establishes minimum standards for the reception of applicants for international protection within Europe. In the past, Member States had different and sometimes inadequate practices. The new Reception Directive, adopted by the European Parliament on 12/06/2013⁹, aims at guaranteeing the highest and most harmonised standards within the Union (Figure 2).¹⁰

Figure 2. Reception Statistics in Belgium

Source: <https://www.fedasil.be/en/statistics>

⁹ Full text available: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?pubRef=-//EP//TEXT+TA+20130612+ITEMS+DOC+XML+V0//EN&language=EN> and see also https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/policies/asylum/reception-conditions_en

¹⁰ The agency responsible for refugee and asylum seeker reception in Belgium is the Federal Agency for the Reception of Asylum Seekers (Fedasil) which is involved in the operational and support missions of the intra-EU agency European Asylum Support Office (EASO). Official website: <https://www.fedasil.be/en>.

Five legal channels of migration to Belgium are also important in understanding the statistical data on migration to Belgium. According to the Belgian Federal Migration Centre, Myria, which is an independent public body¹¹ the first significant decline in immigration in two decades was reported in Belgium as 124,717 international immigrants versus 138,071 in 2001 (*Center fédéral Migration*, 2014: 20). EU citizens comprised 63% of these immigrant populations, followed by migrants from Africa mainly from Morocco from North Africa and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) for sub-Saharan Africa (*Center fédéral Migration*, 2014: 22). In 2012, 11 percent of the Belgian population held a foreign nationality in terms of demographic representation and some research estimates found that around 19 percent of the population was born abroad (Center fédéral Migration, 2014: 29). In 2012, Belgium's main foreign nationalities were Italian, French, and Dutch. Moroccan and Turkish nationals were the most represented in the foreign population from non-EU countries (*Center fédéral Migration*, 2014: 33).¹²

However, it is important to highlight that as the Migration Policy Institute has noted, the absence of reliable migration statistics is also a problem for Belgium in developing a coherent migration policy. It is hard to find accurate and comparable data since measurements and methodologies differ. For example, because of the high naturalisation rates in the past decades, it is difficult to calculate the actual number of people with an immigrant background in Belgium. However, information is not collected on the ethnicity or birthplace of the parents; thus the exact size of the second and third-generation of immigrants are difficult to ascertain.¹³

As Martiniello et al. (2010) summarised migration waves to Belgium over the last five decades have been as follows: (1) a period of (predominantly low-skilled) labour migration during the 1960s and the first half of the 1970s; (2) labour migration was ended with the so-called migration-stop in 1974 and limiting migration to family reunification, matrimonial migration, asylum claims and EU-migration; (3) a period of continued family reunification and matrimonial migration in the 1980s and 1990s and (4) since the decade following 2000, continued family reunification and matrimonial migration has been complemented by increasing asylum migration and migration from the new European Union member states such as Poland and Bulgaria and Romania following the consecutive EU-enlargements.

Then on May 1 2009, Belgium opened its labour market completely, which allows all EU citizens to work without labour cards and were also granted access to the 'service vouchers' system within the labour market. As it was the case in France, the debates surrounding migrants in Belgium are not confined to those of Muslim-origin. In fact, immigration from Eastern Europe is also debated in terms of Polish migration to Belgium after the 2004 enlargement.¹⁴ To that end, these studies cover various topics including Peirs et al. (2008) focusing on how the Belgian media portrayed Polish migrants, Galent et al. (2009) studying the relations between Polish employees and Belgian employers, as well as Grzymała-

¹¹ Source: <https://www.myria.be/en/about-myria>

¹² For a detailed discussion of these statistics see Mandin, 2014.

¹³ Source: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/belgium-country-permanent-immigration>

¹⁴ See also Van Mol (2016); Tecmen (2020: 23)

Kazłowska (2005) studying undocumented Polish migrants in Brussels. Furthermore, in their study on migration and integration dynamics regarding Polish migrants in Belgium, Levrau et al. (2014: 309) note that Belgium remained the seventh most popular destination for Polish immigrants (Galent et al., 2009), while Brussels and Antwerp were the most preferred cities (Perrin and Rajabaly, 2005).¹⁵

Integration policies in Belgium

In terms of general discourses on migrant integration in Belgium, Mandin (2014: 8) identifies three main trends: a) culturalization of social problems in which there is an overemphasis on religious practices or the Islamic headscarf, and problems experienced by some foreign-born populations (higher rates of unemployment, urban marginalisation, etc.) constructed in the context of cultural characteristics and differences; b) crystallisation of integration discourses around Muslims which has become prevalent after 9/11 and the growing concerns over Belgian fighters in Syria; c) relative invisibility of some migrant populations in the integration question in which the discourses focus mainly on non-EU nationals, particularly from a poor socio-economic background, while some EU nationals are omitted.

Due to the cultural and linguistic plurality of Belgium, it is often considered a crossroads of two cultures (Verlot, 2001; Van Avermaet and Gysen, 2009). In Belgium integration policies developed quite late because, until the 1980s, the assumption was that immigration was provisional and the migrants themselves and the host countries considered migrant communities to be temporary parts of the labour force. For instance, Turkish migration to Belgium was conceived as a temporary family project, but it moved towards chain migration, whereas Moroccan emigration, particularly the Berbers, was politically motivated; thus they were less likely to return to Morocco (Kaya and Kentel 2009: 20; see also Lesthaeghe, 2000: 19-20; and Manço and Kanmaz, 2005).

To that end, due to the diversity of migrants communities, their emigration motivations and integration experiences since the 1960s, there is not a Belgian model of integration. Therefore, “facing at the same time a migration situation and a post-migration situation, Belgium has to design integration policies for newcomers as well as integration policies for the second and third generations” (Martiniello, 2003: 230-231). Furthermore, regional differences in Flanders and Wallonia were also observed. Flanders’ approach was inspired by the Dutch multicultural model following multicultural policies, whereas the Walloon government instituted anti-exclusion policies inspired by the French republican model. (Martiniello, 2003).

By the mid-1990s, Wallonia slowly opened up to issues linked to cultural diversity, whereas Flanders, like the Netherlands, emphasised social and economic considerations in its integration policies. The region of Brussels, which is a crossroads between Belgian national

¹⁵ See also Van Mol and De Valk (2016).

groups, newcomers, and “old migrants is trying to develop its own approach by combining elements from the available models (ibid.).

Acquiring Belgian nationality has been one of the most lenient procedures in Europe since the 2000s. Legislators have aimed to promote integration through basic requirements such as years of residence and some legal documents. Currently, there are several procedures to become Belgian. Adults can become a citizen if he/she is registered in the population register; stayed legally in Belgium for at least 5 years; shows knowledge of one of the national languages and shows social integration and participation in economic life. Minors can become Belgian citizens if they are under the age of 5 and have been born abroad to a Belgian parent born abroad or if they are under the age of 12 and have been born in Belgium to parents who have resided in Belgium for over 10 years. Alternatively, the Chamber of Deputies can also grant naturalisation if one has an exceptional record (in sports, art).¹⁶

Furthermore, Ataman et al. (2017) note that while Nationality Code in 1984 introduced simple requirements to acquiring Belgian citizenship, foreign nationals can apply for Belgian citizenship through the procedure of naturalisation after (1) being minimum 18 years old, (2) officially residing in Belgium for at least 2 years of marriage and (3) having knowledge of Dutch, French or German and proof of social integration defined and regulated by their region of residence. Many of the legal residents who have not chosen to become citizens are first-generation immigrants and, ‘since applying for Belgian citizenship involves producing birth certificates that in many cases simply do not exist, thousands never bothered’. Therefore, one can claim that the immigrants who still do not hold Belgium citizenship are the ones who spent the most years as immigrants in the country (Ataman et al. 2017)

Regional differences in integration policies

According to Marco Martiniello (1995), the main differences between Flemish and Walloon integration policies can be explained by exploring civic and cultural nationalism. In Belgium and Wallonia, the Francophone approach of immigrant integration is prevalent, which is inspired by the French model. And owing to this influence, the Francophone governments have not recognised ethnic-cultural groups as specific entities in their regional and national policies. As Martiniello (1995) notes in Wallonia, the nation is defined as a political community based on constitution, laws and citizenship, with a lesser emphasis on culture, heritage, history and values. By the same token, Flanders implements cultural nationalism, in which there is a heavy emphasis on language proficiency and the importance of ethnic, cultural identities which are rooted in the Flemish nationalist movement.¹⁷ As Loobuyck and Jacobs (2010) argue, cultural nationalism makes it more difficult for newcomers to be integrated into the host community because the main goal is to maintain and protect a common culture, language, and territory (see also Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2006). These

¹⁶ Source: <https://www.brussels.be/belgian-nationality>

¹⁷ For discussions on the significance of language as an indicator of belonging and inclusion, see Woolard, and Schieffelin, 1994; Irvine, Gal, and Kroskrity, 2009; Simpson, 2003.

contrasting views on the “nation” create further differentiation leading to the fact that citizenship and integration policies in Flanders more politicised than those of Wallonia.

As Ilke Adam (2010) discusses, this is also a result of the fact that Flanders has historically pursued more cultural, financial, and political history which became apparent with the rise of right-wing political parties in the 1990s, as well as the rise of minority nationalism and politicised sense of migration and integration. A more recent example from the Flemish administration is the Flemish Parliament’s President Jan Peumans’ speech in 2011 in which he stated that

The paradox remains: although the Flamings do not – as other nations – like to exhibit their identity. Flanders has become without a doubt more self-confident. The Flemish sub-state aspires to counter this lack of identity and to support Flemish identity that should lead to nation-building. But this awareness of common interests has not yet sunk in to convince the entire population of it (quoted in Pulinx and Van Avermaet 2015: 347).

Belgian national immigration and integration debates show that Flanders has a different public and political opinion than Belgium’s French-speaking component. There is less reticence in Wallonia and Brussels against the regularisation of illegal migrants. And apart from the Flemish politicians, French-speaking politicians were not opposed to voting rights for foreign residents, and revising the open law on nationality is not a priority. The Flemish side’s presence of nationalist parties may explain that difference. Especially since the most extreme and famous Flemish nationalist political formation, VB, who always argues against regularisation, voting rights, etc., without nuance. Therefore, most Flemish political parties are afraid of the far right’s increasing popularity, if they seem too constructive and transparent on migration issues. But, not the only issue is the direct and indirect influence of extreme right and nationalist parties. To defend their position, almost all the Flemish parties use mixed ‘nationalist’ arguments (on autonomy and identity). They want more economic migration because the Flemish economy needs a more open labour market; they also want naturalisation requiring language acquisition (Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2009: 34; Phalet and Swyngedouw, 2003).

Many examples demonstrate the distinction between Flemish and Francophone. Although headscarves in the Francophone education system were actively discouraged or banned, Flemish schools took a more proactive approach (Verlot, 2001). However, the Flemish attitude changed intensely after 2000, resulting in a ban on all religious symbols in all Flemish community public schools on September 11, 2009. Note that a law banning the full-face veil entered Belgium in July 2011. The law forbids any apparel that obscures the wearer’s identity in areas like parks and sidewalks. Samia Belcacemi and Yamina Oussar, two Belgian-Muslim women, challenged the 2011 veil ban, claiming the law violated religious liberty as they asserted that they wear the niqab voluntarily. In 2017, the European Court of Human Rights ruled that Belgium’s clothing ban was, in fact, legal under the European Convention on Human Rights, and it was “necessary in a democratic society” as it sought to

protect “the rights and freedoms of others.”¹⁸ Moreover, there is no clear framework for resolving immigrants’ problems in Wallonia and unlike Flanders immigration is not formulated in cultural terms but rather in terms of economic marginalisation, social ex/inclusion and citizenship (Martiniello, 1995:142-3; 2007, see also Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2009: 36).

As Rea (2007) and Jacobs and Rea (2006) emphasise, intermediaries such as labour unions or cultural, political and social associations modelled after those of the communities’ home countries, served to shape integration approaches within these communities. This also led to considerable differences between the Flemish and Walloon regions. In regard to Muslim-origin migrants, the 1990s were also marked by attempts to institutionalise Islam, the second largest religion after Catholicism, to seek recognition in Belgium (Rath, Groenendijk, Penninx, 1991). Meryem Kanmaz (2002: 99) notes that the path to successful recognition of Islamic religion can be seen as linked to Belgian authorities’ unilateral initiative, with no demand or even request from Muslim communities themselves hence recognition was rushed and there was no consultation or contribution from these communities. Kanmaz (2002) also argues that this hasty institutionalisation was a response to the international climate and problematic minority policies.

¹⁸ There is a vast amount of literature on the headscarf public debate in Belgium: for a discussion of gender and headscarf see Coene and Longman, 2008, for a discussion of the headscarf and Belgian citizenship see Bousetta and Jacobs, 2006.

	Policy emphasis for integration of settled immigrants	Policy for newcomers	Foreign inspiration
Flemish Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognition of the existence of ethno-cultural minority groups - general and category policies - cooperation with, and support of, immigrant self-organisation 	Citizenship trajectories (include language courses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dutch (and Anglo-Saxon) ideas of group-based multiculturalism - Dutch model of <i>inburgering</i>
Francophone Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - individualistic approach - general policies using socio-economic indicators - only indirect targeting of immigrant groups (for instance, in certain neighbourhoods) 	No specific policy (but punctual projects are being financed)	French assimilationist/republican model

Source: Jacobs and Rea 2006: 14 cited in Kaya and Kentel 2009: 22.

In 2004, the Flemish government accepted the Communal Elections Act, which allowed non-citizens to vote in local elections in 2004 (OECD, 2006: 168). This was an updated 'strategic plan for minority policy', called 'living together in diversity'. A wide variety of operational goals and policy measures to be taken in the period 2004-2010 are listed. Moreover, in April 2009, Flemish parliament accepted a new integration decree centred on emancipation and equal participation of certain target groups, accessibility of regular services, and diversity living together.

It is striking that the decree has not only the equal participation and emancipation of the immigrant population as subject, but also the whole society. One of the main aims for the near future is to promote the coexistence in diversity by all citizens and to further the intercultural competence of political and social institutions. As per this policy document, living together in a diversified society is every citizen's responsibility (Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2009: 34).

Based on these requisites for citizenship, in their study of citizenship and integration in Belgium, Reinhilde Pulinx and Piet Van Avermaet (2015) argue that Flanders exemplifies how integration is gradually being replaced by moral citizenship. Legal citizenship is the formal, juridical rights and duties of a citizen as an individual. In contrast, moral citizenship is the expectation of internalising the shared values and mores of the group even if they are not commonly defined (Schinkel 2008, for an examination of the Netherlands from this perspective see Schinkel 2009; Schinkel and Van Houdt 2010). Consequently, the concept of citizenship has shifted from a dynamic and contextualised process that shapes itself through social networks in daily practice to citizenship as an 'achievement.'

One of the many factors that deem the relations between integration and citizenship in Belgium is the federal structure of the state (see Mandin 2014: 9). As Belgium is a federalised state, it has a citizenship policy at the national level and integration policies at

the regional level. Therefore, regional governments do not have a say in the citizenship policies, but they can develop their understandings of integration based on their culture and history. As discussed below, one of the important aspects of such integration policies is the language proficiency requirement in the Flanders case. In other words, “migration policy is mainly a competence of the Belgian government within an international (European Union) legal framework, and migrant policy is mainly a local competence of the communities, regions and cities” (Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2009: 32). This means that the federal government takes on the policies regarding formal citizenship, which includes: “(1) migration policy, voting rights for foreigners, anti-discrimination and anti-racism policies; (2) entrance to the country; (3) permanent residency, and (4) acquisition of nationality” (Pulinx and Van Avermaet 2015: 343). This also means that policies in education, integration, language, housing, and the religion of migrants, are competences of the regional governments.

Furthermore, at the federal level, the Impulse Fund for Migration Policy (FIPI), which aims to fund public or private initiatives to improve the participation of migrants and the Urban Policy (*Politique des Grandes Villes*), supports urban renovation in major cities and supports migrant integration policies. There are also counter-discrimination agencies like the Center for Equal Opportunity and the Fight against Racism (CECLR) (Mandin 2014: 10).

In Flanders there are also various agencies carrying out integration policies, which include: i) reception desks (*Onthaalbureaus*) responsible for the first contact with migrants and for the coordination of their integration program working with the Flemish office of Employment and professional training (*Vlaamse Dienst voor Arbeidsbemiddeling*); the Dutch House (*Huis van het Nederlands*); adult education centers; basic education centers; and linguistic university centers; ii) working together with the reception desks, the Flemish Centre for Minorities renamed “Intersection Migration- Integration” in 2010 promotes harmonious cohabitation in a context of diversity, equality of opportunities and respect of fundamental rights through information, training or policy recommendations (Mandin 2014: 10).

In Wallonia, General Direction of Social Action and Health (DGASS) is responsible for migrant integration. DGASS, which supports integration policies by financing the Regional Centers for Integration (CRI), associations involved in integration actions, and projects focused on integration. Seven regional integration centers (CRI) enforce and integrate initiatives and policies at the local level. Created by decree in 1996, these centres are located in seven Walloon cities with large migrant populations, which include Charleroi, Liège, Namur, La Louvière, Mons, Tubize and Verviers. The CRI has many responsibilities such as implementing integration activities in areas such as work, social life, housing and health; promoting the training of foreign populations; producing relevant data on foreign populations; orienting people in integration processes; evaluating local initiatives; promoting cultural, social and economic participation of foreign people; and promoting intercultural relationships. Moreover, this division of labour is also mirrored in the list of ministers on the different political levels: on the Belgian national level, there is a coordinating minister of migration since 2008, while in the Flemish government (2004-9 and 2009-2014), there ‘civic integration’ (*inburgering*) minister who is responsible for all minority policies (Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2009: 32).

Studies on citizenship and integration in Flanders often make use of comparisons with the Netherlands due to the integration courses called '*inburgering*' (citizenisation or becoming a citizen) (e.g. Eisinga, Billiet, Felling, 1999; Thissen, Fortuijn, Strijker, Haartsen, 2010; Gysen, Kuijper, Van Avermaet 2009; Rakic, 2001; Verhoeven, De Pauw, Kloots, 2004). Pulinx and Avermaet (2015: 340) note that "this implies that immigrants are not seen as citizens before migration, or at least not citizens of the 'right kind' living by moral standards reconcilable with the host society". This creates moral scrutiny which applies to all migrants in Belgium, including Turks, Moroccans and Eastern-Europeans. Significantly, Pulinx and Van Avermaet (2015: 341) state that first-generation migrants, as well as second and third-generation migrants, have to demonstrate linguistic proficiency as well as societal knowledge such as an awareness of the culture, heritage and history of Flanders.

In Flanders, integration was introduced through the "strategic plan for ethno-cultural minorities" (1996), and the "minorities' decree" (1998). In 2004, the Flemish government accepted a 'strategic plan for minority policy', called 'living together in diversity' (see (Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2009: 35; Pulinx and Van Avermaet, 2015), which also introduced *inburgering* courses. These courses were modelled after the Netherlands. This was a turn from the policy of reception which aimed at familiarising migrants with the Flemish society and promoting economic participation (Pulinx and Van Avermaet, 2015: 349). The compulsory training programme contains Dutch as a second language, lessons of introduction to Flemish/Belgian society and democratic values, and some help for access to the labour market. "The idea of *inburgering* is controversial in migrant communities because people usually discuss the policy in terms of 'assimilation' and 'obligations', while the policy could actually be legitimised in terms of qualification, empowerment, emancipation and capabilities" (Loobuyck and Jacobs, 2009: 32).

Nonetheless, despite the similarities between the *inburgering* courses in Flanders and the Netherlands; Gysen et al. (2009: 104) argue that unlike the Netherlands

Flanders has not adopted the passing of language tests as a requirement for entrance and residence. Nor has Belgium officially introduced a language condition for citizenship purposes. Despite a similar discourse on political and societal level in both countries Belgium has not installed the same rigid immigration control system with harsh language conditions as in the Netherlands.

Despite the widely argued criticisms of the language requirement in *inburgering* classes, Jan Blommaert (2011) takes on a different view noting that the long-lasting language-ideological debate in Belgium between Dutch-speaking Flemish and French-speaking Walloons was an emblematic argument that signified a larger set of issues. As such, in this case, language has become a proxy for ethnicity (Laitin, 2000:142), which is a particularly important issue for Belgium due to the "one community, one language" principle (which was written into the Belgian constitution in 1961), which favours linguistically homogeneous regions (Van Avermaet and Gysen, 2009). This also leads to criticisms about the significance of the Belgian model as an example for the EU and multilingual societies. For instance, Vogl and Hüning (2010) argue that Belgium not necessarily an example of multilingualism but rather is an example of a European region where the struggle for

linguistic rights led from the establishment of monolingual territories (Flanders and Wallonia).

An example of the language-ideology in Belgium is debated by Ilke Adam and Dirk Jacobs (2014). Adam and Jacobs argue that after 2007 federal elections, and the 2010 election, which led to a new government after a lengthy period, language emerged as one of the most divisive issues among the Belgian communities, which has even led to discussions on dividing the country. In the 2010 federal elections the Flemish Nationalists (N-VA), the prevailing northern ideological group, and the Francophone Socialists (PS) in the south were not able to reach a consensus on decentralisation. However, in December 2011, temporary 'armed peace' between the political elites of both communities were established as a temporary solution until the federal elections of 2014. The 2014 federal elections marked a change in tone, being fought on socio-economic terms, but confirmed the stalemate. The N-VA made further progress, winning 29.8 percent of the vote in the Dutch-speaking community. The PS remained the largest political formation in the south, winning 31.0 percent of the vote in the French-speaking community (André and Depauw, 2015).¹⁹ To sum up, as Thérèse De Raedt (2004) argues while the autochthon population identifies with its regional identity, many foreigners, mostly Muslims, identify with their new (formerly host) Belgian identity. Therefore, in a politically divided Belgium, patriotism generally exists only weakly in the autochthonous population's mentality, expressing their national identity with some derision. Over the past 20 years, however, half a million 'foreigners,' of which a substantial number are Muslims, have chosen Belgian citizenship. Some feel more attached to their new (formerly host) country than the indigenous population. These 'new Belgians' redefine Belgian nationality, national identity and citizenship (De Raedt 2004: 9).

Integration Policies and the Youth

As discussed in the case of Germany (Kaya 2009, 2012), in many Western European countries, including Belgium, Turkish-origin immigrants are among the least favoured minority group by members of the mainstream society (Verkuyten and Kinket, 2000), and Turk adolescents *perceive* more personal and group discrimination as compared to other ethnic groups (Verkuyten 2002). While psychological adaptation among this group is high, sociocultural adaptation remains difficult for migrant Turk youth (Sam 2000; Smila 1987). Importantly, Turkish-origin migrants rely on their ethnic group to cope with acculturation stress (Güngör, 2007; Verkuyten, 2002). In addition, Scheible and Fleischmann (2013: 374) argue that both Moroccan and Turkish-origin migrants can be characterised by severe disadvantages in education and in the labour market (Phalet, 2007; Phalet, Deboosere, and Bastiaenssen, 2007). North African families can be credited with having made a significant effort with regard to their children's schooling and have bridged most of the schooling gap between them and most other (European) immigrant groups in Belgium (Feld and Manço, 2000).

¹⁹ On 25 May 2014 federal elections, regional elections in Flanders, Wallonia, and Brussels, and European elections were held simultaneously, which raised the stakes.

Furthermore, Agirdag, Loobuyck, and Van Avermaet's (2012) regression analysis showed that female teachers, Muslim teachers, younger teachers, and teachers with a four-year college degree have significantly more positive attitudes towards diverse student groups but that teachers employed in schools enrolling a large share of Muslim students, such as more than 50 percent, have more negative attitudes toward Muslim students than other teachers. Agirdag, Van Houtte, and Van Avermaet (2012) note that native pupils exhibit higher global self-esteem in schools with a greater share of immigrant pupils and in those with less ethnic heterogeneity. However, for immigrant pupils, none of the measures of ethnic school composition was initially related to their global self-esteem.

Similar to Muslim minorities in other European countries, the level of religious identification and practise is high among Moroccan- and Turkish-Belgians because of efficient intergenerational transmission of religiosity (Güngör, Fleischmann, and Phalet 2011). The social practice of citizenship, however, is not just confined to the national scale. It is at the local scale where participation in civic institutions and civic actions takes place most frequently. In both of these countries, members of minority and migrant groups have access to opportunities for participation through community and non-governmental organisations. In fact, it has been documented that Turkish immigrants in the European Union are likely to have a strong associational life, dense social networks and a strong sense of community – 35% of Turks in Belgium (Jacobs, Phalet, and Swyngedouw, 2004) are members of an ethnic community. Most of the time, these compartmentalised communities tend to generate their own solidarity networks without communicating with other independent communities to maintain their cultural and religious identities within the host country's public sphere (Manco and Kanmaz, 2005).

Wets (2006: 95) finds that education among the second generation, especially compared to other groups, is still limited but third-generation deviates from the previous ones with a higher rate of university graduates. Significantly, approximately 40 percent of them are female, and early half of the Turkish females who study at this level prefer to study medicine while the male population who reach this level prefer economics, international trade, political science, and the like. While they are clustered in Flemish regions, success rates are higher in French-speaking universities. Seventy percent of those who begin university are able to graduate, which partly stems from the fact that the children do not have language proficiency (Wets, 2006: 95).

In another study, Van Tubergen, and Wierenga (2011) examine the determinants of immigrants' second-language proficiency in Belgium based on data from a large-scale immigrant survey conducted in 1994-96 among Turkish and Moroccan males. Van Tubergen, and Wierenga find that while immigrants invest more in learning the official language of their current region of residence, investing in learning French is usually more desirable because it is a more international language than Dutch. The authors also find that those who migrated at a younger age, those who have been residing in Belgium for a longer time period, those who have received more education-particularly education in Belgium, and those residing in regions with fewer co-ethnics have higher Dutch and French-speaking skills.

Marriage, particularly its impact on chain migration and the integration of Muslims in Europe is a commonly studied topic (cf. Charsley, Bolognani, Spencer. 2017; Timmerman, 2006; Wray, Agoston Hutton, 2014; Çelikaksoy, Nielsen, Verner, 2006; Williams, 2010). For instance, Georges Renier (2001: 24) writes as follows

Societies not only specify rules restricting marriages between close kin, but barriers out of which marriage partners should not be sought. Perhaps the most endogamy rule in Muslim societies is its religious one. Muslim men are allowed women from Christian, Jewish or Muslim faith, yet Muslim women are allowed to other Muslims. Rules of endogamy are, however, not exclusively religious and always as absolute as in this example. Other widespread endogamy rules include social class, village and lineage.

In his study on comparative of consanguineous marriages within Turkish and Moroccan-origin migrant communities, Renier (2001: 32) finds that i) consanguineous marriages are more common among Moroccans than among Turks, ii) consanguineous marriages are more common in Belgium than in the countries of origin. Among Turks in Belgium, for example, kin marriages account for 34% of all marriages while this is the case only for 22% of the marriages in Turkey. This is a first indication for rejecting our hypothesis that the practice of kin marriages decreases with migration; iii) the difference between the country of origin and Belgium is larger for Turks than for Moroccans. It is consistent with earlier observations that the assimilation of Moroccans to more westernised demographic behaviour is proceeding faster than that of Turks (see Lodewijckx, Page and Schoenmaekers, 1997; and Page and Segaert, 1999).

Similar to marriages, another commonly discussed topic is surely the gender aspect of Turkish migration to Belgium. For instance, Christiane Timmerman (2006) shows that since the late 1980s, marriage has emerged as one of the few means by which Turks can legally settle in Western Europe. Timmerman states that the relations between marriage and migration prove to be a key factor in the assessment of gender aspects and the consequences for involvement and inclusion in society and the socialisation of future generations within Western European Turkish communities. A significant finding in doing so is that arranged marriages correspond to the migration ambitions of both the established Turkish communities in Western Europe and the areas of emigration in Turkey. This dynamic is maintained over the years due to the strong Turkish nationalistic identification within the Turkish communities in Western Europe and the hostile climate in which they live.

Another study which explores gender is that of Güngör and Bornstein (2009). This study addresses that gender differences and similarities in acculturation, values, adaptation, and perceived discrimination among middle (14-17 years) and late (18-20 years) adolescents. Interestingly, the study found that girls perceived less discrimination and showed better adaptation compared to boys. While all adolescents valued openness to change and self-transcendence similarly, but older adolescents attached greater importance to their heritage culture and conservatism.

Timmerman et al.'s (2003) exploration of the education levels among the second generation in Belgium also shows that while a growing proportion of second-generation Moroccan and

Turkish youngsters in Belgium are moving on to higher secondary education, this trend is greater among Moroccan youngsters compared to their Turkish peers. The authors note that Turkish girls are still married off at a young age, which inevitably affects their educational opportunities, and despite the higher education participation rates for immigrant youth, the educational gap with Belgian pupils and students remains large, due to socio-economic differences. Timmerman et al. (2003) also emphasise that Islam's significance for second-generation immigrants is changing and a growing number of second-generation youth choose a more secular lifestyle, while an increasingly large group chooses Islamist ideologies or at least a more conscious form of Islam. Islamism can provide a transparent, supportive, and all-encompassing frame of reference for second-generation youth, who often have little to hold onto socially.

Socio-economic disadvantages are the topic of another study conducted by Ellen Quintelier (2009). Quintelier works with the general perceptions on the political participation of ethnic minorities that reveals that immigrants have lower levels of participation, stemming from their lower socio-economic status. Quintelier's research based on a representative survey of 6,330 16-year-olds in Belgium shows that young immigrant people do not have lower levels of political participation, but there are clear differences. As such, participation is influenced by gender, socio-economic situation, mother tongue and sense of group identity, and not by citizenship status, television or religion. Her research concludes that

Firstly, immigrants have lower levels of socio-economic status, which tends to reduce political participation. Secondly, being a young woman appears to *increase* the likelihood of participation, in contrast to expectations. Thirdly, and as predicted, a high sense of group identity, along with the presence of ethnically diverse friends, makes young people more likely to participate (Quintelier 2009: 932).

Fatima Zibouh's (2013) study on Muslim political participation in Belgium has similar findings. Zibouh draws attention to the ethnification of Muslim identity in which country of origin (i.e., Turk, Arab, Moroccan) does not make a difference as their "otherness" is rooted in their religious identity. However, conversely, Ataman, Sener, Noack and Born (2016) found that Turkish youth in Belgium is very much active in conventional ways of participating in politics (e.g. voting) due to being able to vote in local elections.

The emphasis on religious identity is continued in Scheible and Fleischmann's (2013) study on the gender differences in religious practices and the association with gender ideology among second-generation Moroccan-and Turkish-Belgian Muslims argue that while first-generation Muslim-origin migrants display higher levels of religiosity and take on traditional gender roles than second-generation migrants, particularly among second-generation migrant women.

According to data from the European Values Survey, anti-Muslim prejudice and subsequent terrorist attacks in Europe were more common than anti-immigrant prejudice among European majority populations even before September 11, 2001 (Strabac & Listhaug, 2008). Such anti-Muslim attitudes may affect the formation of Muslim minority identities in Europe.

Smits et al.'s (2010) study on the religious practices among Moroccan and Turkish men in Belgium uses data from the Migration History, and Social Mobility Survey collected in 1994-1996 from 2,200 men. They measure religious participation as mosque attendance, fasting during Ramadan, and sacrificing a sheep at the Festival of Sacrifice. They find that religious participation of these two groups depends on both premigration and postmigration characteristics and that religious participation is higher among immigrants who: (1) attended a Koranic school in their country of origin, (2) were socialised in a religious region of their home country, (3) received little schooling, (4) currently live in an area of Belgium with a greater number of mosques, and (5) associate with a high number of co-ethnics.

According to a recent study conducted by Fenella Fleischmann and Karen Phalet (2018), all minorities support national identities less strongly compared to majority youth, but the lowest among Muslims is the national identification. The authors attribute this to public concerns over the insufficient inclusion of immigrant minorities in general, and Muslims in particular, in national identities across Europe. Moreover, significant country variation in group differences in identification suggests that Muslims are more inclusive of some national identities than others. Taking an intergroup approach to the inclusiveness of national identities for Muslims, Fleischmann and Phalet show that, beyond religious engagement, positive intergroup interaction (such as majority friendship) plays a major role in explaining disparities in national identity in multi-group multilevel mediation models, while school experience does not lead to discrimination.

Terrorism Attacks and Extremist Activities in Belgium

As in many other countries, terrorist attacks in Belgium has created an Islamophobic discourse, which has impacted the public and political perceptions of Muslim-origin migrants, as well as the way they perceive threats in daily life (see Crijns, Cauberghe, and Hudders, 2017). On September 30 2003, a Belgian court convicted 18 men for involvement in a terror cell. In October 2004, a Belgian court sentenced eight Sunni Islamic militants to prison terms of up to 5 years for plotting attacks and for links to Al Qaeda. On November 9 2005, Muriel Degauque, a Belgian convert to Sunni Islam, committed a suicide car bomb attack against a US military convoy south of Baghdad.

More recently, in May 2014, Belgium became the first EU country to experience an attack by a -foreign fighter returning from Syria when a man of French origin – Mehdi Nemmouche – opened fire in a Jewish museum in Brussels, killing four people. On November 13, 2015, a coordinated terrorist attack in Paris killed 130 people and injured around 352 others.

On March 22, 2016, two suicide bombers-later identified as ex-convict Ibrahim el-Bakraoui and suspected bomb-maker Najim Laachraoui-launched attacks at Brussels' Zaventem airport, killing 16 people. An hour later, another suicide bomber-identified as Khalid el-Bakraoui-struck the city's metro system, killing 16 people at the Maelbeek station²⁰. On June 20, 2017, soldiers shot and killed an attempted suicide bomber at Brussels Central

²⁰ See <https://www.ict.org.il/Article/1645/The-Brussels-Attacks#gsc.tab=0>

train station after the attacker's bomb failed to detonate. On August 25, 2017, a man with a knife attacked and injured two soldiers near Brussels' Grand Place. The attacker was shot and killed at the scene.

The complex, highly decentralised structure of Belgium's government continues to be a challenge for internal sharing of information and cooperation. Belgium's biggest terrorism threat comes from homegrown terrorists inspired by ISIS. The high number of Belgian foreign terrorist fighters in Syria and Iraq has also generated concern about the attacks by returning jihadists, although fewer have returned than anticipated²¹. Furthermore, with at least 451 foreign fighters who have travelled or attempted to travel to Syria and Iraq, Belgium has the highest number of foreign fighters per capita¹ of all Western countries (Van Vlierden, 2016).

Source: <https://www.ict.org.il/Article/1645/The-Brussels-Attacks#gsc.tab=0>

Furthermore, in 2019, the State Security Service listed 100 organisations in Belgium, which promoted Salafist ideology including mosques, community centres and educational establishments²². Salafism is a tendency of Islam that developed as an anti-imperialist movement in 19th century Egypt, related to the Wahabi movement in Saudi Arabia. It is considered one of the most fundamentalist Islamist movements, associated with terrorist acts (see Roex, 2014; Wagemakers, 2008; Cesari, 2005; Wiktorowicz, and Kaltner, 2003). The State Security Service (VSSE), has asserted that the Salafi movement is gaining momentum in the country with radical Islamists increasing their influence on Belgium's Muslim population. To that end, according to the VSSE, Salafist ideology is considered a threat against Belgian society because Salafists reject democratic institutions and promote

²¹ Source: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/5bcf1fb64.html>

²² Source: <https://www.brusselstimes.com/all-news/belgium-all-news/justice-belgium/55681/state-security-lists-more-than-100-salafist-organisations-active-in-belgium-koen-geens/>

a return to the traditions of the salaf, the first three generations of Muslims.²³ The salafi movement comprises of purists, who avoid politics; activists, who focus on Salafi policies promotion; and jihadists, who promote armed struggle²⁴. As such, the VSSE highlights that Salafi Islam promotes Shari'a law, as well as gender inequality.

As noted by Coolsaet (2019: 46), Belgium has competing paradigms on radicalisation. Coolsaet identifies two main approaches to the relations between the individual and radicalisation. According to this approach, jihadi terrorism is essentially the result of an ideology-driven process. As such, society does not play a significant role in radicalisation. Concluding a comprehensive discussion on radicalisation after an attempted terrorist attack in Verviers, Belgium in January 2015, the president of the Flemish nationalist group in the Flemish parliament thus asserted that 'society can never be blamed for radicalisation' (quoted in Coolsaet 2019: 46). The second approach considers radicalisation to be primarily a context-driven process. Belgian federal prosecutor in charge of terrorism, Frédéric Van Leeuw, also took this position admitting that 'our Western society is part of the problem' in the departure of many foreign fighters. A similar statement was made by Belgium's top police official Catherine De Bolle: What really shocked me, before the attacks and with all that has happened since is that society has failed to include people. There are many who live with us for years, even decades. We didn't succeed in devising a common denominator. They do not really feel as if they are being included, as if they are part of our society, of Belgium (ibid).

Conclusion

As the literature review indicates Belgium's regional differences as shown through ethnolinguistics and citizenship policies leads to diverse scholarship on the country's migration and integration policies. To that end, while Wallonia is inspired by the French Republican model emphasising political unity over others, Flanders' deeply rooted history of nationalism often goes hand in hand with the Dutch model that Flanders follows through multiculturalist policies.

To that end, Belgium, with its multilingual nature, has been a notable example in the EU's emphasis on linguistic diversity. As the literature indicates, this diversity does not result only in regional differences but also in different approaches to language and language proficiency in each region. This form of diversity also stems from historical differences in regard to how the nation and the community are constructed. This varying significance of linguistic proficiency in integration policies is a reflection of the community's history and heritage. This also illustrates the non-uniform nature of migration, integration, and citizenship policies in Europe. While there have been attempts to harmonise and streamline the migration policies of the EU member states, it is still a competence of the member

²³ For a discussion of the EU's understanding of Salafism, see Radicalization Awareness Network (2018).

²⁴ Source: <https://sputniknews.com/europe/201904181074246471-islamic-salafi-movement-belgium/>

states. Significantly, the integration of migrants and refugees are still considered at the national level. Complementing this, public discourses further influence the policy level at the local level, which encompasses the reception of migrant and migrant-origin individuals by their immediate surroundings that are their neighbourhood. As such, as we will explore in the PRIME Youth project, it is essential to look at the everyday lives and the day-to-day interactions of the individuals, which shape the way they articulate their sense of belonging or isolation.

Bibliography

- Adam, I., & Jacobs, D. (2014). Divided on immigration, two models for integration. The multilevel governance of immigration and integration in Belgium. In *The Politics of Immigration in Multi-Level States* (pp. 65-85). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Agirdag, O., Loobuyck, P., & Van Houtte, M. (2012). Determinants of attitudes toward Muslim students among Flemish teachers: A research note. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 51(2), 368-376.
- Agirdag, O., Van Houtte, M., & Van Avermaet, P. (2012). Ethnic school segregation and self-esteem: The role of teacher–pupil relationships. *Urban Education*, 47(6), 1135-1159.
- André, A., & Depauw, S. (2015). A Divided Nation? The 2014 Belgian Federal Elections. *West European Politics*, 38(1), 228-237.
- Ataman, A., Sener, T., Noack, P., & Born, M. (2017). Political participation beyond borders: a comparative analysis of Turkish youth living in home country, Germany and Belgium. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 20(5), 565-582.
- Billiet, J., & De Witte, H. (1995). Attitudinal dispositions to vote for a 'new 'extreme right-wing party: The case of 'Vlaams Blok'. *European Journal of Political Research*, 27(2), 181-202.
- Blaise, P. and de Coorebyter, V. (1997). "La reconnaissance et la représentation de l'Islam" (The Recognition and Representation of Islam), in M.T. Coenen and R. Lewin (eds.), *La Belgique et ses immigrés: Les politiques manquées (Belgium and its Immigrants: Failed Politics)*. Brussels.
- Blommaert, J. (2011) The long language-ideological debate in Belgium, *Journal of Multicultural Discourses*, 6:3, 241-256, DOI: [10.1080/17447143.2011.595492](https://doi.org/10.1080/17447143.2011.595492)
- Bousetta, H. and D. Jacobs (2006) 'Multiculturalism, citizenship and Islam in problematic encounters in Belgium', in T. Modood, A. Triandafyllidou and R. Zapata-Barrero (eds) *Multiculturalism, Muslims and Citizenship. A European Approach*, pp.23-36. London: Routledge.
- Çelikaksoy, A., Nielsen, H. S., & Verner, M. (2006). Marriage migration: just another case of positive assortative matching?. *Review of Economics of the Household*, 4(3), 253-275.
- Cesari, J. (2005). Ethnicity, Islam, and les banlieues: Confusing the Issues. *Social Science Research Council*, 30.
- Charsley, K., Bolognani, M., & Spencer, S. (2017). Marriage migration and integration: Interrogating assumptions in academic and policy debates. *Ethnicities*, 17(4), 469-490.
- Coene, G., & Longman, C. (2008). Gendering the diversification of diversity: The Belgian hijab (in) question. *Ethnicities*, 8(3), 302-321.
- Coolsaet, R. (2019). "Radicalisation: The Origins and Limits of a Contested Concept" in Fadil, N., Ragazzi, F., & de Koning, M. (Eds.). (2019). *Radicalisation in Belgium and the Netherlands: Critical Perspectives on Violence and Security*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Crijns, H., Cauberghe, V., & Hudders, L. (2017). Terrorism threat in Belgium: The resilience of Belgian citizens and the protection of governmental reputation by means of communication. *Public Relations Review*, 43(1), 219-234.
- De Raedt, T. (2004). "Muslims in Belgium: A Case Study of Emerging Identities", *Journal of Muslim Affairs*, Vol. 24, No. 1 (April): 9-30.

-
- Debuissou, M., Docquier, F., Noury, A., & Nantcho, M. (2004). Immigration and aging in the Belgian regions. *Brussels Economic Review*, 47(1), 138-58.
- Dierckx, D., & Van Dam, S. (2014). Redefining empowerment interventions of migrants experiencing poverty: The case of Antwerp, Belgium. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 44(suppl_1), 105-122.
- Drhimeur, L.A. (2020a), Moroccan political system, <https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/en/publications/moroccan-political-system-literature-review/> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3697407
- Drhimeur, L.A. (2020b), The State of the Art on Moroccan Emigration to Europe, <https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/en/publications/state-art-moroccan-emigration-europe/> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3822021
- Eisinga, R., Billiet, J., & Felling, A. (1999). Christian religion and ethnic prejudice in cross-national perspective: A comparative analysis of the Netherlands and Flanders (Belgium). *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, 40(3), 375.
- Fleischmann, F., & Phalet, K. (2018). Religion and National Identification in Europe: Comparing Muslim Youth in Belgium, England, Germany, the Netherlands, and Sweden. *Journal of cross-cultural psychology*, 49(1), 44-61.
- Galent M., Goddeeris I. and Niedzwiedzki D. (2009) *Migration and Europeanisation*. Krakow: Nomos.
- Grzymała-Kazłowska, A. (2005). From ethnic cooperation to in-group competition: Undocumented Polish workers in Brussels. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 31(4), 675-697.
- Güngör, D. (2007). The interplay between values, acculturation and adaptation: A study on Turkish–Belgian adolescents. *International Journal of Psychology*, 42, 380–392.
- Güngör, D., & Bornstein, M. H. (2009). Gender, development, values, adaptation, and discrimination in acculturating adolescents: The case of Turk heritage youth born and living in Belgium. *Sex Roles*, 60(7-8), 537-548.
- Gungor, D., Fleischmann, F. and Phalet, K. (2011). Religious identification, beliefs, and practices among Turkish Belgian and Moroccan Belgian Muslims: Intergenerational continuity and acculturative change. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 42:1356-74.
- Gysen, S., Kuijper, H., & Van Avermaet, P. (2009). Language testing in the context of immigration and citizenship: The case of the Netherlands and Flanders (Belgium). *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 6(1), 98-105.
- Ireland, P. R. (1994). *The Policy Challenge of Ethnic Diversity: Immigrant Politics in France and Switzerland*, Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Ireland, P. R. (2000). "Reaping What They Sow: Institutions and Immigrant Political Participation in Western Europe", in R. Koopmans and P. Statham (eds.), *Challenging Immigration and Ethnic Relations Politics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Irvine, J. T., Gal, S., & Kroskrity, P. V. (2009). Language ideology and linguistic differentiation. *Linguistic anthropology: A reader*, 1: 402-434.
- Jacobs, D. and Rea, A (2006). "Construction and Import of Ethnic Categorisations: 'Allochthones' in the Netherlands and Belgium", Working Paper, Fondazione Eni Enrico Mattei, Milano, Italy (April).
- Jacobs, D., and Rea, A. (2006). Construction and Import of Ethnic Categorisations: 'Allochthones' in the Netherlands and Belgium.

-
- Kanmaz, M. (2002). The recognition and institutionalisation of Islam in Belgium. *The Muslim World*, 92(1/2), 99.
- Kaya, A. (2009). *Islam, Migration and Integration: The Age of Securitization*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Kaya, A. (2015). "Islamophobia as an Ideology in the West: Scapegoating Muslim-Origin Migrants," in A. Amelina, K. Horvath, B. Meeus (eds.), *International Handbook of Migration and Social Transformation in Europe*, Wiesbaden: Springer: 281-294.
- Kaya, A. (2016) Critical Heritages (CoHERE): The use of past in political discourse and the representation of Islam in European Museums, Work Package 2- Critical Analysis Tool (CAT) 1: The rise of populist extremism in Europe.
https://eu.bilgi.edu.tr/media/files/Kaya_Critical_Analysis_I_Populism_Theory.pdf
- Kaya, A. (2017). Critical Heritages (CoHERE): The use of past in political discourse and the representation of Islam in European Museums, Work Package 2- Critical Analysis Tool (CAT) 2: Lost in Diversity and Unity.
https://eu.bilgi.edu.tr/media/files/Kaya_Critical_Analysis_II_Populism_Lost_in_Diversity_and_Unity_6.pdf.
- Kaya, A. (2019). *Populism and Heritage in Europe: Lost in Diversity and Unity*, Routledge.
- Kaya, A. (2020) "State of the Art on Radicalisation: Islamist and Nativist Radicalisation in Europe", Istanbul Bilgi University, Working Paper 12,
https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/media/document/2020/04/28/kaya_wp_12_2020.pdf DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3773199
- Kaya, A. and Kentel, F. (2004). Euro-Turks: A Bridge, or a Breach, between Turkey and the European Union?, OSCE Conference on Tolerance and the Fight against Racism, Xenophobia and Discrimination, Brussels, 13 and 14 September 2004.
- Laitin, D. D. (2000). What is a language community?. *American Journal of political science*, 142-155.
- Levrau, F., Piqueray, E., Goddeeris, I., & Timmerman, C. (2014). Polish immigration in Belgium since 2004: New dynamics of migration and integration?. *Ethnicities*, 14(2), 303-323.
- Loobuyck, P., & Jacobs, D. (2006). The Flemish immigration society: Political challenges on different levels. *New citizens, new policies*, 105-123.
- Loobuyck, P., & Jacobs, D. (2009). Nationalism, multiculturalism and integration policy in Belgium and Flanders. *Canadian Issues*, S29.
- Mandin, J. (2014). *An overview of integration policies in Belgium*. Available at: <http://diana-n.iue.it:8080/handle/1814/33133>
- Martiniello, M. (1995). European citizenship, European identity and migrants: towards the post-national state. *Migration and European integration: The dynamics of inclusion and exclusion*, 37-52.
- Martiniello, M. (2003). Belgium's immigration policy. *International Migration Review*, 37(1), 225-232.
- Martiniello, Marco (1997). "Quelle participation politique?" (What Kind of Political Participation?), M.T. Coenen and R. Lewin (eds.), *La Belgique et ses immigrés: Les politiques manquées (Belgium and its Immigrants: Failed Politics)*. Brussels: De Boeck Université: 101-120.
- OECD. (2006). *International migration outlook*. OECD publishing.

-
- Peirs M, De Roo P, Vanhove T, et al. (2008) Gluren bij de nieuwe burenen. Een onderzoek naar de beeldvorming over Poolse immigranten in de Vlaamse dagbladders. Report, Arteveldehogeschool Ghent, Belgium.
- Phalet, K. (2007). Down and out: The children of migrant workers in the Belgian labour market. In *Unequal chances: Ethnic minorities in Western labour markets*, edited by Anthony F. Heath and Sin-Yi Cheung. Oxford: Proceedings of the British Academy.
- Phalet, K., Deboosere, P. and Bastiaenssen, V. (2007). Old and new inequalities in educational attainment: Ethnic minorities in the Belgian Census 1991-2001. *Ethnicities* 7:390-415.
- Phalet, K., & Swyngedouw, M. (2003). Measuring immigrant integration: the case of Belgium. *Studi Emigrazione*, 773-804.
- Pulinx, R., & Van Avermaet, P. (2015). Integration in Flanders (Belgium)–Citizenship as achievement: How intertwined are ‘citizenship’ and ‘integration’ in Flemish language policies?. *Journal of Language and Politics*, 14(3), 335-358.
- Quintelier, E. (2009). The political participation of immigrant youth in Belgium. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 35(6), 919-937.
- Radicalisation Awareness Network (2018) “Islamist Extremism: A Practical Guide”, https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/networks/radicalization_awareness_network/ran-papers/docs/ran_factbook_islamist_extremism_december_2019_en.pdf
- Rakic, V. (2001). Converge or not converge: the European Union and higher education policies in the Netherlands, Belgium/Flanders and Germany. *Higher Education Policy*, 14(3), 225-240.
- Rath, J., Groenendijk, K., & Penninx, R. (1991). The recognition and institutionalisation of Islam in Belgium, Great Britain and the Netherlands. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 18(1), 101-114.
- Rea, A. 2007. *L'étude des politiques d'immigration et d'intégration des immigrés dans les sciences sociales en Belgique francophone*. In: M. Martiniello, A. Rea, F. Dassetto (eds.). *Immigration et intégration en Belgique francophone. État des savoirs*. Louvain-la-Neuve: Bruylant, pp. 103-140.
- Reniers, G. (2001). The post-migration survival of traditional marriage patterns: Consanguineous marriages among Turks and Moroccans in Belgium. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 21-45.
- Roex, I. (2014). Should we be scared of all Salafists in Europe? A Dutch case study. *Perspectives on Terrorism*, 8(3), 51-63.
- Sam, D. (2000). Psychological adaptation of adolescents with immigrant backgrounds. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 140, 5–25.
- Scheible, J. A., & Fleischmann, F. (2013). Gendering Islamic religiosity in the second generation: Gender differences in religious practices and the association with gender ideology among Moroccan-and Turkish-Belgian Muslims. *Gender & Society*, 27(3), 372-395.
- Schinkel, W. (2008). The moralisation of citizenship in Dutch integration discourse. *Amsterdam LF*, 1, 15.
- Schinkel, W. (2010). The virtualisation of citizenship. *Critical Sociology*, 36(2), 265-283.
- Schinkel, W., & Van Houdt, F. (2010). The double helix of cultural assimilationism and neo-liberalism: citizenship in contemporary governmentality. *The British journal of sociology*, 61(4), 696-715.

-
- Simpson, P. (2003). *Language, ideology and point of view*. Routledge.
- Smila, M. (1987). Cultural identity in young immigrants: A study of sociocultural conditions and ethnic identification among Turks and Yugoslavs in Stockholm (Rep. No. 7). Stockholm, Sweden: University of Stockholm, Center for Research in International Migration and Ethnic Relations.
- Smits, F., Ruiter, S., & Van Tubergen, F. (2010). Religious practices among Islamic immigrants: Moroccan and Turkish men in Belgium. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 49(2), 247-263.
- Swyngedouw, M. (1998). The extreme right in Belgium-of a non-existing front national and an omnipresent Vlaams Blok.
- Swyngedouw, M., & Ivaldi, G. (2001). The extreme right utopia in Belgium and France: The ideology of the Flemish Vlaams Blok and the French Front National. *West European Politics*, 24(3), 1-22.
- TA, H. B., & Jacobs, D. (2006). Multiculturalism, citizenship and Islam in problematic encounters in Belgium. In *Multiculturalism, Muslims and Citizenship* (pp. 34-47). Routledge.
- Tecmen, A. (2020) "Migration, Integration and Citizenship in France between 1990 and 2018: The State of the Art", https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/media/document/2020/06/09/literature-review-on-france_june_2020.pdf
- Thissen, F., Fortuijn, J. D., Strijker, D., & Haartsen, T. (2010). Migration intentions of rural youth in the Westhoek, Flanders, Belgium and the Veenkoloniën, The Netherlands. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 26(4), 428-436.
- Timmerman, C. (2006) Gender Dynamics in the Context of Turkish Marriage Migration: The Case of Belgium, *Turkish Studies*, 7:1, 125-143, DOI: 10.1080/14683840500520642
- Timmerman, C. (2006). Gender dynamics in the context of Turkish marriage migration: the case of Belgium. *Turkish Studies*, 7(1), 125-143.
- Timmerman, C., Vanderwaeren, E., & Crul, M. (2003). The second generation in Belgium. *International migration review*, 37(4), 1065-1090.
- Van Avermaet, P., & Gysen, S. (2009). One nation, two policies: Language requirements for citizenship and integration in Belgium. *Language testing, migration and citizenship: Cross-national perspectives on integration regimes*, 107-124.
- Van Mol, C. (2016). Migration aspirations of European youth in times of crisis. *Journal of youth studies*, 19(10), 1303-1320.
- Van Mol, C., & De Valk, H. (2016). Migration and immigrants in Europe: A historical and demographic perspective. In *Integration processes and policies in Europe* (pp. 31-55). Springer, Cham.
- Van Tubergen, F., & Wierenga, M. (2011). The language acquisition of male immigrants in a multilingual destination: Turks and Moroccans in Belgium. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 37(7), 1039-1057.
- Van Vlierden, G. (2016), "Foreign Fighters in Syria and Iraq – An Updated Per Capita Count," Emmejihad, April 26, 2016.
- Verhoeven, J., De Pauw, G., & Kloots, H. (2004). Speech rate in a pluricentric language: A comparison between Dutch in Belgium and the Netherlands. *Language and speech*, 47(3), 297-308.
- Verkuyten, M. (2002). Perceptions of ethnic discrimination by minority and majority early adolescents in the Netherlands. *International Journal of Psychology*, 37, 321–332.

-
- Verkuyten, M., & Kinket, B. (2000). Social distances in a multiethnic society: The ethnic hierarchy among Dutch preadolescents. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 63, 75–85.
- Verlot, M. (2001). *Werken aan integratie. Het minderheden- en onderwijsbeleid in de Franse en Vlaamse gemeenschap*.
- Vogl, U., & Hüning, M. (2010). One nation, one language? The case of Belgium. *Dutch crossing*, 34(3), 228-247.
- Vrielink, J. (2014). 'Islamophobia' and the law: Belgian hate speech legislation and the wilful destruction of the Koran. *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law*, 14(1), 54-65.
- Wagemakers, J. (2008). Framing the "Threat to Islam": Al-Wala'wa Al-Bara'in Salafi Discourse. *Arab Studies Quarterly*, 1-22.
- Walgrave, S., & De Swert, K. (2004). The making of the (issues of the) Vlaams Blok. *Political Communication*, 21(4), 479-500.
- Wets, J. (2006). The Turkish community in Austria and Belgium: The challenge of integration. *Turkish Studies*, 7(1), 85-100.
- Wiktorowicz, Q., & Kaltner, J. (2003). Killing in the name of Islam: Al-Qaeda's justification for September 11. *Middle East Policy*, 10(2), 76-92.
- Williams, L. (2010). *Global marriage: Cross-border marriage migration in global context*. Springer.
- Woolard, K. A., & Schieffelin, B. B. (1994). Language ideology. *Annual review of anthropology*, 23(1), 55-82.
- Wray, H., Agoston, A., & Hutton, J. (2014). A family resemblance? The regulation of marriage migration in Europe. *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 16(2), 209-247.
- Zibouh, F. (2013). Muslim political participation in Belgium: an exceptional political representation in Europe. *Muslim Political Participation in Europe*, 17-33.

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